

A Quasi-experimental Study to Assess Feasibility of Novel Medical Chatbot Based on the 'Extremities' Chapter of Boger Boenninghausen's Characteristics & Repertory

Dr. Kusum¹, Dr. Sunita Sachin Dhotre², Prof. Dr. Anita S Patil^{1*}

¹Research Scholar, Department of Repertory, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Homoeopathic Medical College, Pune.

²Associate Professor, Department of Computer Engineering, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) College of Engineering, Pune.

³H.O.D. of Department of Repertory, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Homoeopathic Medical College, Pune

Abstract

Background: Existing homeopathic software provides professional and medical homeopaths the opportunity to cross-index large amounts of data; to repertorise more accurately because of the time that is saved in the process, in comparison to previous generations of practitioners that relied on repertorising by hand. The problem of time and energy consumption during case taking still persists because the doctor must enter the information obtained during case taking manually.

AI is being used in various fields, including healthcare, education, aeronautics, etc. AI continues to be promising in the form of various expert systems and decision trees but chatbot platforms are lacking due to various reasons in homeopathy. So, a novel functional chatbot application based on the 'Extremities' chapter of Boger Boenninghausen's Characteristics & Repertory is proposed.

Methods: A prospective, open-label, quasi-experimental study was conducted on thirty patients (Age group: 20 to 80 years) to assess the feasibility of the chatbot application. Patients filled in their details of complaints of extremities using the chatbot application. The accuracy of the chatbot application was tested by repertorising the same symptoms with Zomeo Elite software and scores were compared. Medicines were prescribed based on symptom similarity. The response to the treatment was assessed by changes in VAS scores before & after the intervention, and ORIDL scoring at the first and last follow-up.

Results: The correlation coefficient between (i) the number of common symptoms selected by physician & patient and the number of drugs common in the repertorial result of patient and physician; (ii) the number of symptoms selected by patients and number of symptoms selected by physician; (iii) the number of symptoms selected by the physician and the number of common symptoms selected by the physician and patient was 0.350 ($P<0.05$), 0.797 ($P<0.001$) and 0.594 ($P<0.001$) respectively. There was 100 percent accuracy in the repertorial result of the application. In 65% of observations, chatbot showed the prescribed medicine in top 10 list.

Conclusions: This study demonstrated the potential effectiveness of the chatbot application for the practitioner as a time-saving medical assistant which lessens manual work by simple and quick selection of simillimum.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Chatbot; Homeopathy; Repertory.

Introduction

The homeopathic materia medica contains information about homeopathic medicines. Today approximately 5,000¹ homeopathic medicines are known to the profession. No human can reminisce about all the medicines and their symptoms. The vast nature of homeopathic materia medica & inability of the human mind to remember it led to the development of repertory. The homeopathic repertory helps to locate the required symptoms together with the medicine or group of medicines.

There are many types of repertories like Clinical repertories, Card repertories, Concordance repertories and Logical-utilitarian group of repertories. Each repertory is used for different functions like finding simillimum, as a

reference book, finding a drug for the second prescription, studying homeopathy with modern pathology, etc.^{1,2} Searching for rubrics manually and doing paperwork for repertorisation takes away the valuable time of physicians. Conventional repertories were initially very beneficial, but are nowadays becoming too large for pragmatic use in the future. This criticism of repertories in print form is annulled by homeopathic software like HOMPAT, Rapid Aid to Drug Aimed Research (RADAR), Vision, Mac repertory, STIMULARE, I.S.I.S., Mercurius, Organon 96, and Kentian. Software are mainly categorised into two i.e., Processing software and Reference/database. With the help of processing software like Kentian & Organon 96, case-taking & data processing both are possible. Kentian & Organon 96 both have an in-built Artificial Intelligence (AI) system that automatically carries out the analysis and evaluation of symptoms instantly. In addition, they also classify the miasm and offer different ways of repertorisation. Reference software like CARA, RADAR, and HOMPAT have a large database and they provide a quick reference to different types of materia medica, directories, dictionaries, and many repertories.³

Mac repertory has 17 repertories and 48 materia medica. It allows us to hunt for any word, phrase, idea, or theme hidden anywhere in the materia medica and repertories. It provides easy access to the confirmatory information of materia medica. I.S.I.S. uses the latest technology & offers features like attaching photographs to rubrics, remedies, or patient record notes, and running videos in the new remedy screen section. It provides updated, easy-to-use repertories, materia medica & dictionary all in one screen, and information related to drug proving of new remedies.^{1,3} However, the problem of time consumption during case-taking persists despite using these processing tools because the practitioner must enter the information obtained during case-taking manually.

1.2 Rationale and Knowledge Gap

Computers can mimic the decision-making & problem-solving power of the human mind with the help of AI. AI is being used in various fields, including healthcare, education, aeronautics, etc.⁴. Chatbots are computer programs with AI that can have natural human conversations and are being used in health care for various functions.⁵ The use of chatbots in healthcare presents the opportunity to improve the daily work of medical practice and resource savings of the clinic, giving physicians free time to give better treatment to patients.⁶ AI continues to be promising as expert systems and decision trees, but chatbot platforms are lacking due to various reasons in homeopathy. So, a chatbot application based on the 'Extremities' chapter of Boger Boenninghausen's Characteristics & Repertory (B.B.C.R.) is proposed to reduce the labor and save the time, the physician spends in taking details from the patient and searching rubrics for the repertorisation of the case. It will decrease the waiting time of patients & the physician will also be freed up to give better treatment to patients.⁷

BOGER BOENNINGHAUSEN'S CHARACTERISTICS AND REPERTORY

B.B.C.R. is one of the grand works of Dr. C.M. Boger, based on the Boenninghausen's Repertory of Antipsoric Medicines. This repertory has modalities for each part assembled at the end of concerned section of repertory, as well as a section toward the end of the book devoted to general modalities. It is brought up to date and made far more valuable by adding remedies and a synoptic materia medica as one section of the book. It belongs to the logical utilitarian group of repertory. Its structure can be divided into three sections. The first section contains localized symptoms arranged in a head-to-toe scheme. The second section contains generalized symptoms, & the third section is the 'Concordances' section of Boenninghausen's T.P.B. There are fifty-three chapters in the book. In each chapter, rubrics are arranged as a complete symptom. There are no separate headings for Location and Sensations. But they follow an order, i.e., Sensations are listed alphabetically after Location. Time, Aggravation, Amelioration, Concomitant, and cross-reference follow them.

✦ The '**location**' rubric is further divided into subdivisions of parts, with each part having rubrics like 'side' & 'extending to'. The end of the location is marked by a horizontal line.

✦ The '**sensation**' rubric is further divided into sub-rubrics under which parts are stated. Different sensations and pathological conditions are stated under 'Sensations'.

✦ **Time:** It is further divided into major subdivisions like daytime, morning, forenoon, noon, etc. There is no subdivision into specific hours, unlike Kent’s Repertory.

✦ **Aggravation:** It includes factors that increase the complaint. In chapters lacking separate sections for concomitants, some of the concomitants are mentioned under this subsection.

✦ **Amelioration:** It includes factors that decrease the complaints. This section has a lesser number of rubrics in comparison to ‘Aggravation’.

✦ **Concomitants:** This is a major contribution of Boger to Homeopathy. In most of the chapters, they are well explained. Only a few chapters, like Mind and Respiration, are there, which enlist only a group of medicines. The ‘Fever’ chapter is rich in concomitants.

✦ **Cross-reference:** This section is used to clear confusion regarding similar rubrics. It is not present at the end of all chapters.

About Extremities chapter of B.B.C.R.

The chapter “Extremities” is divided into Upper Extremities and lower Extremities. Rubrics are arranged as a complete symptom, i.e., location, sensation, modality & concomitant. Both chapters have separate sections on time, aggravation, and amelioration. Cross-reference is absent in both chapters. In many places, the side affinity of the medicine is also present in brackets. E.g. in the Upper Extremities chapter, under the rubric ‘Shoulder’, it is shown as **Shoulder, sh.:** *chel.* (r), *kali-m* (r), *kalm.* (l), **Phos.** (l)

Here “r” means right and ‘l’ means left.

□ In the ‘Upper Extremities’ chapter, the rubric arrangement is as follows:

Rubric for the entire muscular & fleshy part of arms → Side → Location → Sensations → Time → Aggravation → Amelioration.

Under the ‘Sensation’ section of the ‘Upper Extremities’ chapter, rubrics either represent sensations or some symptoms under which locations are present as sub-rubrics. Only one exception is there, i.e., ‘Axillary glands’ which is a location under which sensations are present. □ In the ‘Lower Extremities’ chapter, the rubric arrangement is as follows:

Side → Locations → Sensations → Time → Aggravation → Amelioration.^{3, 8, 9}

Representation of the Extremities chapter in various repertories is shown in Table 1¹⁰⁻¹⁴

Table 1: Representation of the Extremities chapter in various repertories		
S.No.	Book Name	Representation of Extremities chapter
1	Homoeopathic Medical Repertory ¹⁰	Repertory is printed in 2 columns on each page. Chapters and rubrics both are alphabetically arranged. Locations in the ‘Upper Extremities’ & ‘Lower Extremities’ sections of B.B.C.R are present as separate chapters in this repertory.
2	Therapeutic Pocket Book (T.P.B.) ¹¹	Extremities chapter is represented as ‘Upper extremities’ and ‘Lower extremities’. The difference between B.B.C.R. & T.P.B. is that here these chapters contain rubrics related to locations only. Sections related to sensation, time, aggravation, or amelioration are absent in this.

3	Repertory of Homoeopathic Materia Medica ¹²	Extremities chapter is the largest chapter of this book & contains rubrics related to both the upper and lower extremities. It is the least useful chapter for repertorisation & is criticized for overparticularisation. Location is not present as rubrics instead they are present at the second last under the main rubric. Arrangement of rubric follows STME pattern i.e., Side, Time, Modalities, Extensio .
4	Boericke's Repertory ¹³	Extremities chapter is present as "Locomotor System" in this repertory. The main rubric is written in bold capital & subrubrics are written in Roman. Mostly main rubric represents locations under which sensations are arranged alphabetically as sub-rubrics.
5	Boger Synoptic Key ¹⁴	Extremities chapter is represented as "Upper limbs" and "Lower limbs" under regional repertory. The repertory is printed in 2 columns on each page. Chapter names are written in bold capital, rubrics are written in capital, and sub-rubrics are written in Roman. Cross-references are given after the remedies for that rubric & sub-rubric. Synonyms are given just after the rubric in Bold Roman letters with the prefix see.

1.3 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:

This study aims to develop a chatbot application based on the "Extremities" chapter of Boger Boenninghausen's Characteristics Repertory to evaluate its feasibility in daily practice and incorporate the best possible technology for modernizing homeopathic repertories and achieving higher accuracy and precision in the case-taking process.

2. Methods

A prospective, open-label, quasi-experimental study was conducted at Bharati Vidyapeeth Homeopathic Medical College. Patients attending the OPD of the institute were screened. Thirty patients with complaints covered under the Upper Extremities and Lower Extremities chapter of B.B.C.R. were enrolled in the study. Out of thirty patients, 63% were male and 37% were female belonging to the age group of 20-80 years. Based on the preset criteria (inclusion and exclusion), patients were invited to participate in the study and were explained about the study protocol, risks, and benefits of participation. Voluntary written informed consent was taken from the patients before enrolling them as research participants. Patients filled in their details of complaints related to extremities using the chatbot application. The rest of the complaints were asked in detail through interviews. Medicines were prescribed to the patients based on symptom similarity.

The accuracy of the chatbot application was tested by repertorising the same symptoms with Zomeo Elite software and scores were compared. While checking the accuracy of the result, the calculation of the scores was done manually as the Zomeo software does not follow the gradation of remedies according to B.B.C.R. Our chatbot application follows the gradation of the B.B.C.R. The feasibility of the application was tested by finding the correlation between (i) the number of common symptoms selected by the physician & the patient and the number of drugs common in the repertorial result of the patient and the physician; (ii) the number of symptoms selected by patients and the number of symptoms selected by the physician (iii) the number of symptoms selected by the physician and the number of common symptoms selected by the physician and patient. The response to the treatment was assessed by the changes in Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) scores before & after the intervention, and Outcome Related to Impact on Daily Living (ORIDL) scoring at first and last follow-up. Follow-up differed from patient to patient depending upon the severity and need of the case.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients who satisfy the case definition

- Patients of both sexes.
- Patients of any socio-economic status.
- Patients of all age groups.
- Patients who can read, write & interpret the English language.
- Pre-diagnosed cases with the already-conducted investigations.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients who require surgical intervention.
- Patients who are terminally ill.
- Patients who do not give consent for the study.

Intervention

Homeopathic drugs, as detailed in the standard Homeopathic Materia Medica and the Homeopathic Pharmacopoeia (India/US), were used in the study. The drugs identified for the trial were procured from a GMP-compliant pharmaceutical firm.

Selection of remedy:

After case-taking, repertorisation was done using Zomeo Elite software, and indicated homeopathic medicine was selected based on the totality of symptoms.

Selection of potency and repetition of doses:

The medicines were administered in various potencies such as 6x, 30C, 200C, and 1M., depending upon the requirement of the case.

Drug Administration:

Medicines were administered in globule, powder, or tablet form. The medicine was taken orally by the patient.

Chatbot Application

Chatbots are computer programs with AI that can have natural human conversations and are being used in health care for various functions. The proposed system is an interactive chatbot that aids homeopathic physicians in prescription by collecting symptoms from the patients, mapping them to the rubrics of the concerned chapter of the B.B.C.R. database, and then listing medicines with their scoring. Its front end is based on HTML & CSS, and the back end is based on the Django framework of Python to host the application. The data of patients and physicians is saved in an SQLite database. There are different models for user data, doctor profile, patient profile, patient medical history, and patient case sheet. These models are designed using the Django framework, which converts directly into tables in the actual database. It provides pre-defined options for the patients to choose an answer. The patients have to answer around twelve questions. The number of questions varies according to the type of problem. Most of the questions have a single answer, but some questions have the option to select multiple answers. Once the patient has answered all the questions, the case sheet is automatically saved. After that, the chatbot uses an algorithm to calculate the scoring of the medicines based on the symptoms of the patient for the doctor to view it. (System Design and System flow of the chatbot application are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively)

Figure1: System design

Figure 2: System flow for the chatbot application

User Registration

To use the system, one has to register by providing data such as name, phone number, username, password, address, etc. (shown in Figure 3). After registration, the user can log in with a user ID and password. The user can be a doctor or a patient.

Figure 3: User Interface for Registration

Figure 4: Patient screen

Patient module:

After login, the patient must create a new case sheet to start interaction with the chatbot (shown in Figure 4). A case sheet is a sheet that gathers information about the problems faced by the patient. If he has already created a case sheet, then he can edit it from the start.

Case sheet module:

The case sheet has the data about the complaint of the patient. A tree structure is followed in the case sheet,

i.e. once the case sheet is created for a particular part, selecting sub-locations/sensations/ameliorations/aggravations of that particular part becomes necessary. If a patient has a complaint related to another part, then a new case sheet must be formed for that part. The created case sheets will be visible to doctors and the patient to which it belongs.

Doctor module:

Like patients, doctors have to log in as well. They can also update their medical profile. After logging in successfully, doctors can view the case sheets of the patient and the medicines suggested by the algorithm (See Figure 5, 6 and 7). They can make changes to the case sheet by selecting a general rubric if the patient has selected a sub-rubric with a smaller number of medicines.

Figure 5: Physician screen after log in

Casesheet name: ac2

Q1. What is the location of your complaint?	Upper Extremities
Q2. What is the sub-location of your complaint?	Shoulder
Q3. What is your complaint?	Pain
Q4. On which side is it present? (if it is present on both side, choose Shoulder)	Shoulder
Q5. How did it begin?	Gradual
Q6. Since how long it is present?	Years
Q7. Is there any history of trauma preceding its onset?	No
Q8. How do you describe its severity?	Mild
Q10. What term can best describe the pain?	Pain, simple->Shoulder
Q26. At what time of day it increases?	None of the above
Q27. What factors increase it?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Raising arms <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stretching out limb <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Winter, in
Q28. What factors decrease it?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pressure, external <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rubbing
Q29. Are there any other symptoms?	None of the above

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Figure 6: Output Screenshot of options selected by the patient being displayed to the physician

Medicine	Scores
Cupr.	12
Caust.	11
Ph-ac.	11
Spig.	11
Acon.	10
Agn.	10

Figure 7: Output Screenshot of medicines in the repertorial result being displayed to the physician

Data visualization module

Data visualization is the representation of the data using standard visuals like charts, plots, infographics, and even animations. Doctors can use this module to gain meaningful visions from the data stored in the database. They can select the question in which they need to conjure up the data and three options are provided to plot the charts (bar graph, pie chart, and Donut chart).

Features:

- The doctors can insert single-correct questions from 1-25 and multi-correct questions from 26-35.
- The questions that are permitted to be inserted are more than the original requirement making the application scalable later on.
- The code is modular and full of functions which makes the code easy to debug.

3. Results

In the study, 20% of patients were of age 20-35 years, 36% were aged between 35-50 years, 27% were aged between 50-65 years and 17 % of the patients had an age above 65 years. There were 19 males and 11 females. *Rhus-tox* was prescribed to 20% of the patients and *Arnica*(*Arn*), *Bryonia* (*Bry*), *Nux-vomica* (*Nux-vom.*), and *Pulsatilla* (*Puls*) were prescribed to 10% of the patients each at first prescription.

Before treatment, the VAS Score was 5.83 ± 1.73 , and it reduced to 2.50 ± 1.48 after treatment. The ORIDL scores for the main complaint in the last follow-up showed significant improvement. More than half of the patients (53.3%) had moderate improvement (score of 2), and more than one-third of the patients (36.66%) had major improvement (score of 3) or complete recovery (score of 4). Only 10% of patients had mild improvement (score of 1). The ORIDL scores for overall well-being in the fourth follow-up showed significant improvement. 70% of the patients had moderate improvement (score of 2), and 10% had major improvement (score of 3). Only 20% of patients had no improvement (score of 1). [Refer to Tables 2 and 3]

Table2: Distribution of patients according to Outcome related to the impact on daily living (ORIDL) score for the main Complaint				
ORIDL Score	First follow-up		Fourth follow-up	
	Number of patients	Percentage	Number of patients	Percentage
0	5	16.7%	0	0.00%
1	18	60.0%	3	10.00%
2	5	16.7%	16	53.33%
3	1	3.3%	7	23.33%
4	1	3.3%	4	13.33%

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to ORIDL score for overall well-being.				
ORIDL Score	First follow-up		Fourth follow-up	
	Number of patients	Percentage	Number of patients	Percentage
1	25	83.33%	06	20.00%
2	4	13.33%	21	70.00%
3	1	3.33%	03	10.00%

There was 100 percent accuracy in the repertorial results of the application. While checking the accuracy of scores, a problem was faced as many rubrics are missing in Zomeo software such as in the ‘Aggravation’ section of the ‘Upper Extremities’ chapter, 18 rubrics are missing between sitting and yawning. Under the ‘Time’ section, the rubric ‘evening’ is missing. Another problem was due to drugs missing under various rubrics in Zomeo. E.g. In the ‘Upper Extremities’ chapter, drugs are missing under the following rubrics:

1. Left – 8 drugs are missing
2. Right- 8 drugs are missing
3. Joints of, in general- 7 drugs are missing
4. Drawing, shoulder- 4 drugs are missing
5. Dryness of skin, hands- 3 drugs are missing
6. Eruption, forearm- 3 drugs are missing
7. Pain, simple, joints- 3 drugs are missing
8. Twitching, hands- 5 drugs are missing
9. Time- Night: 3 drugs are missing
10. Aggravation, Motion, in general-2 drugs are missing (Bryonia and Staphysagria)

In the ‘Lower Extremities’ chapter, drugs are missing under the following rubrics:

1. Right- 6 drugs are missing
2. Thigh, inner side- 5 drugs are missing
3. Calves- 5 drugs are missing
4. Joints, in general- 5 drugs are missing
5. Knee, joint- 4 drugs are missing
6. Pain, simple- Joint, knee- 4 drugs are missing
7. Time-Night- 5 drugs are missing
8. Aggravation, motion- of affected limb- 4 drugs are missing
9. Aggravation, standing-5 drugs are missing
10. Amelioration, motion-continued- 2 drugs are missing

The correlation coefficient between (i) the number of common symptoms selected by the physician & the patient and the number of drugs common in the repertorial result of the patient and the physician; (ii) the number of symptoms selected by patients and the number of symptoms selected by physician; (iii) the number of symptoms selected by the physician and the number of common symptoms selected by the physician and patient was 0.350

($P < 0.05$), 0.797 ($P < 0.001$) and 0.594 ($P < 0.001$) respectively. In 65% of observations, chatbot showed the prescribed medicine in top 10 list.

4. Discussion

During homeopathic consultation, homeopathic physicians make use of materia medica & repertories in digital or print form to find the specific remedy for the case. The homeopathic materia medica contains information about homeopathic medicines and repertory is an index of symptoms-rubrics organized in an alphabetical order for which various medicines are indicated. Although repertory resolves the difficulties faced due to the vast nature of materia medica, it has given rise to some new difficulties. Each repertory has a fixed structure and internal rules for using it. Searching for rubrics manually and doing paperwork for repertorisation takes away the valuable time of a physician.¹⁵ This criticism of repertories in print form is annulled by various homeopathic software.

Today, most of the prevailing software is meant to make the process of repertorisation easier¹⁶, and a few software, like Kentian and Organon 96 help in case processing. However, the problem of time and energy consumption during case taking persists despite using these processing tools because the doctor must enter the information obtained during case taking manually. AI makes computers more intelligent and has a great capacity for improving the quality of health care. Chatbot is one of the several applications of AI. Chatbot has been used in health care for purposes like answering/asking questions, giving information related to diseases, and reviewing the results of clinical tests. AI has been applied as expert systems and decision trees but chatbot platforms are lacking in the field of Homeopathy. In this study, a novel functional chatbot application based on the 'Upper Extremities' & 'Lower Extremities' chapter of B.B.C.R was developed and its feasibility was checked in daily practice.

The proposed chatbot application will act as an assistant to the homeopathic practitioners because it helps in selecting a remedy for the patient by collecting symptoms from the patient, mapping those symptoms to rubrics of the B.B.C.R., and showing the list of medicines based on total scoring in descending order. It reduces the labor and time, the physician spends in taking details of the patient and searching rubrics for repertorisation of the case. This decreases the waiting time of patients & the physician is also freed up to give better treatment to patients. It has a data visualization module that doctors can use to extract meaningful visions from the data stored in the database. They can select the question in which they need to conjure up the data and three options are provided to plot the charts. It also has a feature in which doctors can edit the case sheet of the patient.

As the sample size of the study was small and data for checking the feasibility of the application was not showing normal distribution, the paired-t test and Spearman's rank correlation coefficient were used for statistical analysis. While checking the accuracy of scores, the problem was faced as many rubrics and drugs are missing in Zomeo software indicating that the proposed chatbot application is better than conventional software because its gradation of remedies is according to the B.B.C.R. and drugs are not missing under various rubrics (Table 4).

Gradation of remedies in B.B.C.R is equivalent to	Gradation of remedies in Zomeo
5	4
4	3
3	2
2	1
1	1

While checking the feasibility of the application, it was seen that the difference in the number of common symptoms selected by the physician and the patient was due to the difference in the interpretation of the meaning of the rubrics. Many symptoms/ rubrics selected by the patient contained either single medicines or a small number of medicines which was not useful for repertorisation, so physician chose general rubric or another rubric. The chatbot application being a machine does not iterate a few terms and group them to a single combined symptom. It always picks out individual specific symptoms, owing to which there always comes a difference between the number of symptoms by the doctor and the patient & also the number of common symptoms is limited. Despite the symptoms selected by the patient and physician are different, the number of drugs that are common after individual repertorisation by chatbot and physician is 8.

The proposed chatbot application has few limitations, so further work is needed to improve its effectiveness. First, we need to incorporate more chapters into our application as the functionality of this application is limited to the extremities chapter. The total number of chapters in B.B.C.R. is 52 (excluding Concordances and Word index), so there is still a lot of work to do. Second, we have to add the feature of showing the number of symptoms covered by the medicines along with their scoring in the result. Third, the meaning of similar rubrics should be added to avoid confusion. Fourth, for choosing the exact location of the problem, a picture of the body should be added, so that the patient does not select the wrong words for the location. Fifth, while choosing options for sub-rubrics, the patient should be able to choose multiple answers. Sixth, at present, the application does not add scoring of the problem in separate locations, and for each location, a patient has to generate a separate case sheet and scoring is displayed separately for each location. So, the feature of showing cumulative scoring of all locations needs to be added to make it feasible in daily practice.

5. Conclusions

With the promising results it is shown that the chatbot application will develop into a time-saving medical assistant for the doctor that gathers every minor and significant detail of the case, maintains the confidentiality of the record, stores the records securely, and lessens the doctor's manual work by simple & quick selection of simillimum. The widespread use of the application will expand the reach of homoeopath's service to remote locations.

However, as the functionality of the chatbot is restricted to the 'Extremities' chapter and limitations were found during the study, so suggested changes should be made.

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Conflict of Interest Statement:

Conflicts of Interest: None

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Figure 1: System Design

Figure 2: System Flow for the chatbot application

Figure 3: User Interface for registration

Figure 4: Patient screen

Figure 5: Physician screen after log in

Figure 6: Output Screenshot of options selected by the patient being displayed to the physician

Figure 7: Output Screenshot of medicines in the repertorial result being displayed to the physician

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Table 1: Representation of the Extremities Chapter in various repertories

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to Outcome related to the impact on Daily living (ORIDL) score for the main complaint

Table 3: Distribution of patients according to ORIDL score for overall well-being

Table 4: Gradation of medicines in Zomeo and B.B.C.R.

Statement of Ethics:

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of BVDUHCM (Protocol No: BVDUHCM/PG/2021/14) and informed consent was obtained from all individual participants.